

QUALITY INDICATORS OF WHEAT

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Abstract: Establishment of the optimal norms of mineral fertilizers against the background of the introduction of organic fertilizers (manure) for the Polovchanka wheat variety under the conditions of old irrigation of light gray soils and the rationale for their positive effect on growth, development, crop, damage.

The main goal of the research is to solve the influence of the quality of the regime on the technological indicators that show the quality of the Polovchanka grain, a variety of winter wheat, under conditions of light gray soil in the Kashkadarya region.

Introduction. Our country has achieved grain independence thanks to the intensive development of grain crops on irrigated lands. This victory plays an important role in fully meeting the food needs of our people in the context of the global financial crisis.

In recent years, breeders have grown high-yielding varieties of winter wheat. For the successful introduction of these varieties into agricultural production, it is necessary to test them in various soil and climatic conditions of the country and develop appropriate agrochemical measures for each variety.

Due to the difficult natural and climatic conditions of the republic, the soils developed in different regions differ sharply in their properties and characteristics, and therefore, in each individual state of each agricultural crop, including grain, appropriate agrotechnical and agrochemical measures are required.

Therefore, it is important to develop an agricultural technology for growing each variety of winter wheat in different regions, including a feeding system aimed at improving the technological parameters that determine grain quality.

The main reason for the low protein content of winter wheat grown on irrigated lands is the lack of nitrogen during the growth and development of plants and the violation of the ratio of nutrients in the process of mineral nutrition in general. As a result, the protein content in the grain is reduced, this problem can be solved by applying nitrogen fertilizers and adapting the nutrient medium of the soil to the needs of the plants. soils, especially in the Kashkadarya region.

The main task in this case is to determine the criteria and terms for applying nitrogen fertilizers in accordance with the requirements of the plant variety and specific soil conditions, as well as the correct application of mineral fertilizers with organic fertilizers. proportions.

- Kashkadarya region is irrigated with light gray background soil conditions with organic fertilizers (manure), fertilizers $N_{180} P_{90} K_{60}$ and $N_{210} P_{110} K_{70}$ standards, when applying agrochemical soil conditions, can satisfy the nutrient needs of winter wheat and improve the nutritional regime of the soil in period of growth and development of plants. As a result, the germination, growth and development of winter wheat of the Polovchanka variety is accelerated, and the growing season is reduced to 8 days, the sign of late ripening is reduced.

- Fertilizer rates $N_{180} P_{90} K_{60} + 30$ t / g and $N_{210} P_{110} K_{70} + 30$ t / g in the ratio of fertilizers of the genital organs of winter wheat variety Polovchanka to vegetative organs increases the technological parameters that determine the quality of grain: grain mass, natural weight, vitreousness, flour yield, increases the amount of protein and gluten in the grain and provides high economic efficiency by increasing the grain yield and improving the quality of autumn wheat Polovchanka.

When growing winter wheat on irrigated light gray soils of the Kashkadarya region against the background of 30 t / ha of manure, the norms of mineral fertilizers $N_{180} P_{90} K_{60}$ and $N_{210} P_{110} K_{70}$ should be applied together. improve the nutrient regime of the soil during the growth and development of plants, increase the absorption of essential nutrients by plants, ensure normal

growth and development of plants, shorten the growing season to 8 days and reduce late maturation.

Fertilizer $N_{180} P_{90} K_{60} + 30$ t / g and $N_{210} P_{110} K_{70} + 30$ t / g fertilizer with an increase in the yield of grain of winter wheat variety Polovchanka As a result of an increase in the amount to 1.1%, an increase in the amount of protein to 5.2 centners per hectare and gluten up to 11.6 centners per hectare.

Of course, the main part of the vegetable protein necessary for the human body must be provided by cereal grains. However, because wheat and other grains are much cheaper, easier, and more convenient to grow than legumes, more grains are grown, and the human body gets its protein primarily from wheat grains.

For this reason, one of the main problems that attracts the attention of scientists is to provide mankind with vegetable protein.

The weight of 1000 grains, natural weight, vitreousness, flour consumption and other indicators are important physical and technological quality indicators that determine the quality of grain and are associated with agroecological, agrotechnological and genetic characteristics of the grown grain.

The research results show that the winter wheat variety Polovchanka is grown without the use of fertilizers and mineral fertilizers at the rate of 38 g per 1000 grains mixed with 30 t/ha. When grown from natural weight 1000 grains. was 40 grams or an increase of 2 grams.

The recommended rate of mineral fertilizers for this wheat variety is $N_{180} P_{90} K_{60}$, which is 41 grams per 1000 grains, otherwise manure and mineral fertilizers are not used. There was an average increase of 3 grams compared to the control . .

A further increase in the weight of 1000 grains was observed with the combined use of manure and mineral fertilizers, which was 43 grams or 5 grams more than in the control variant without fertilizers.

The high weight of 1000 grains led to an increase in the weight of grain grown both under the influence of manure and mineral fertilizers.

An increase in grain mass and natural weight was observed in proportion to the degree of grain glassiness and flour yield in proportion to the norms and forms of fertilizers used.

Grain viscosity was 73.5% in the control variant without fertilizers and 1.6% compared to the control when applying manure at the rate of 30 t/ha; with the introduction of the recommended norms of mineral fertilizers, it increases by 1.9%, with an increase in the recommended norms of mineral fertilizers by 2.5%, with the simultaneous use of both types of fertilizers with an increase of 3.1-3.4%. An increase in the vitreous luster of the grain was also observed. The yield of grain flour in the control variant without fertilizers was 73.3%, 0.9% compared to the control when mixed manure was applied with 30 t/ha of mineral fertilizers. 1.1% at the recommended, 1.5% at higher rates of mineral fertilizers. When combined with manure and mineral fertilizers, an increase in flour yield by 2.1–2.2% was observed, and in the feeding mode, an increase in grain quality was noted.

Another important indicator of grain quality is flour consumption, and if the grain is of good quality, flour consumption will increase. This is due to the fact that if the grain is dark and crumbly, the proportion of reserve substances will be higher than that of the husk. The same situation manifested itself in an increase in flour consumption as the feeding regimen for the winter wheat variety Polovchanka increased. This is due to the fact that the consumption of flour from grain grown in the control variant without fertilizers was 73.3%, and the consumption of flour from grain with the use of mixed manure of 30 t/ha was 74.2%. flour yield is 0.9% more than. At the same time, flour consumption at the recommended rate of mineral fertilizers was 74.4%, which is 1.1% compared to the control variant, when the recommended rate of mineral fertilizers was exceeded. The flour yield was 1.5% higher than in the control variant, which was 74.8%, 4-75.5%, which is 2.1-2.2% more than in the control variant.